

REPUBLIC OF YEMEN
UNIVERSITY OF ADEN
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING
THERMAL SECTION

A seminar in
**DIAGNOSING OF CENTRIFUGAL
PUMP**

Prepared by :

Samer Sameer Abdulrahman Hayel 081001

Supervisor :

Dr. Maan Garada

2013

Acknowledgment

At the beginning I thank Allah for his help and guidance , and I cannot express my deep thanks to Dr. Maan Garada who gave me a lot of the instructions and get me to what is good for this research . The effort made by me and the valuable comments of Dr. Maan are what makes this seminar in a wonderful , prestigious scientific and professional form .

Finally, I would like to express my most sincere gratitude to my family because without their support and encouragement, I could not have completed this work on time .

THE CONTENTS	PAGE NO.
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2. System Related Problems	3
1.2.1 Suction pipe	3
1.2.2 Pump unit	4
1.2.3 Delivery Pipe	5
1.3. Piping (Suction And Discharge) Related Problems	6
1.3.1 Suction pipe	6
1.3.2 Pump unit	8
1.3.3 Delivery Pipe	8
1.4. Mechanical Related Problems	10
1.4.1 Pump unit	10
1.4.2 Pipelines	16
CONCLUSION	17
REFERENCES	18

List of Figures	PAGE NO.
Fig.1.1. Centrifugal pump system	2
Fig.1.2.1. Proper location of the suction pipe	3
Fig.1.2.2. Air pocket in suction pipe	3
Fig.1.2.3. Accumulation of air or gas in the high spot	3
Fig.1.2.4. Wrong rise of the suction pipe	4
Fig.1.2.5. Flow in the pipe bend	4
Fig.1.2.6. Best operation point	4
Fig.1.2.7. Good discharge pipe practice	5
Fig.1.3.1. Types of valves in suction side	6
Fig.1.3.2. Suction recirculation	7
Fig.1.3.3. Examining the pressure side of the inlet vanes for suction recirculation damage	7
Fig.1.3.4. Installation of the impact head tube to detect suction recirculation	8
Fig.1.3.5. Discharge recirculation	9
Fig.1.3.6. Damage to the pressure side of the vane from discharge recirculation	9
Fig.1.4.1. Axial thrust	10
Fig.1.4.2. Radial thrust	11
Fig.1.4.3. Piezoelectric pressure transducers mounted on the pump	12
Fig.1.4.4. Babbitt fatigue	13
Fig.1.4.5. Bearing wipe on a bearing due to temporary loss of lubricant	13
Fig.1.4.6. Corrosion on lead-based babbitt bearing	14
Fig.1.4.7. Components of sealing and packing	15
Fig.1.4.8. Types of misalignment	15

Diagnosing of Centrifugal pump

1.1 Introduction

The centrifugal pumps have widely use in pumping applications comparing to the other types of pumps and the person who deals with the centrifugal pumps will face many problems .

In this paper we try to mention how to diagnose the different problems of the centrifugal pump system in simple and quick way and that is by classifying the reasons of the system problems into three categories which we will take each of them individual :

1. System related problems : occur because of design flaw.
2. Piping (suction and discharge) related problems : usually caused by air lock .
3. Mechanical related problems : occur because of air leaks in the system , worn out impellers and mouth ring ... etc .

We also mentioned the different problems due to each reason and distributed them into the three different sides of the system (suction , pump unit and discharge) .

It is important to know the different parts of the centrifugal pump system and being familiar with each component to be easy for you to diagnose the problem of the system . The main component parts of a centrifugal pump system :

- **Pump unit** : consists of :-
 - Impeller: It is a wheel or rotor which is provided with a series of backward curved blades or vanes. It is mounted on a shaft which is coupled to an external source of energy (usually an electric motor) which imparts the required energy to the impeller thereby making it to rotate.
 - Casing: It is an airtight chamber which surrounds the impeller. It is similar to the casing of a reaction turbine.
- **Suction Pipe**: It is a pipe which is connected at its upper end to the inlet of the pump or to the centre of the impeller which is commonly known as eye. The lower end of the suction pipe dips into liquid in a suction tank or a sump from which the liquid is to be pumped or lifted up. The lower end of the suction pipe is fitted with a foot valve and strainer. The liquid first enters the strainer which is provided in order to keep the debris (such as leaves, wooden pieces and other rubbish) away from the pump.. It then passes through the foot valve to enter the suction pipe. A 'foot valve' is a non-return or one-way type of valve which opens only in the upward direction. As such the liquid will pass through the foot valve only upwards and it will not allow the liquid to move downwards back to the sump.

- **Delivery Pipe:** It is a pipe which is connected at its lower end to the outlet of the pump and it delivers the liquid to the required height. Just near the outlet of the pump on the delivery pipe a delivery valve is invariably provided. A delivery valve is a regulating valve which is of sluice type and is required to be provided in order to control the flow from the pump into delivery pipe.

Fig.1.1. Centrifugal pump system

1.2. System Related Problems

There are many problems caused by design flaw , so before constructing any pumping system we should study carefully the requirements of the system, to design a proper one and to avoid any problems that may appears in the future .

We will discuss these problems which caused in each of the three parts :

1.2.1 Suction pipe :

- When the supply pipe of liquid to the reservoir located near to the suction pipe , this may result leakage of air to the system as shown below .

Fig.1.2.1. Proper location of the suction pipe

- Sometimes the designer put small foot valve .
- Sometimes the bents in the piping traps air pockets causing water hammering which shocks on the piping that may even damage the joints.

Fig.1.2.2. Air pocket in suction pipe

- Suction side should be arranged to discourage the accumulation of air or gas in the high spot .

Fig.1.2.3. Accumulation of air or gas in the high spot

- Suction line should constantly rise towards the pump and high spots should be avoided .

Fig.1.2.4. Wrong rise of the suction pipe

- Most pump manufacturers would strongly discourage fitting a pipe bend straight onto the suction flange of the pump.

Fig.1.2.5. Flow in the pipe bend

- Suction pipe should be equal to pump nozzle diameter, or preferably one size larger, never smaller .

1.2.2 Pump unit :

- Pumps are usually chosen to operate at their maximum efficiency point, within the preferred zone of operation.

Fig.1.2.6. Best operation point

- Make sure that the pump has been chosen to work at the required suction height. Every pump is designed to work at a certain range of pressure and flow condition . The net positive suction head required (NPSHR) is a performance characteristic of the pump, and is established by test . For any system to work, it must be designed such that the net positive suction head available (NPSHA) of the system is equal to or exceeds the net positive suction head required (NPSHR) by the pump.
- Physical properties of the different component in the pumping unit should be evaluated carefully with respect to the properties of the fluid you pump , the ambient temperature ...etc.
- Some positive head and flow rate with pumps of low specific speed, but at very low efficiency may be produce by the reversed rotational. So correct rotation of the driver , it should be verified before coupling it to the pump , and the speed of driver should be suitable for the pump (not slow or fast) .
- Flow rate and efficiency probably will be much reduced and the power consumption increased because of the reversed impeller mounted on the shaft .
- Sometime an improper packing with incorrect grade for liquid being handled , check the packing manufacturer for correct grade. Manufacturers of gland packing will recommend different packing materials for different fluids. Some are suitable for high temperatures. Some can stand the corrosive effects of chemicals or other fluids.
- Check if the cooling liquid not provided for the water-cooled stuffing box .
- Pumping fluids with higher viscosity than that which is the pump designed for will produce lower pressures and flow .

1.2.3 Delivery Pipe:

- Non return valve, [where fitted] should be downstream of valve, in order to protect it against water hammer .
- Pipe bends should not be close to the pump, else vibration may result .
- Gate-valve stem should be parallel with shaft axis.

Fig.1.2.7. Good discharge pipe practice.

A slow diffuser /expander section is followed by substantial length of straight pipe, clamped before the first bend is encountered.

1.3. Piping (Suction And Discharge) Related Problems

The problems related to piping usually caused by air leak to the system or by a fatigue on the pipes or may be due to problem of the valves in the suction and deliver sides .

We will discuss these problems which caused in each of the three parts :

1.3.1 Suction pipe :

- Make sure that the valves are really open. Sometimes valve indicators show that they are in open position while actually they are jammed shut. Gate valves and flap check valves are particularly susceptible to these conditions. The position of the flap check valve disc is difficult to confirm without opening up the valve. Sometimes the worn or broken gear linkage of butterfly valves may also show an error in the valve opening positions.

The easiest way to check whether the valves are opened or closed is to check the pressure gauges at the discharge end of the pump. A higher than normal running pressure means that the valve at the discharge end is closed. While there is no pressure and flow at the user end, the pressure is indicated at the pump. In this test, make sure that the pressure gauge itself is in good condition.

Fig.1.3.1. Types of valves in suction side

- A steady crackling noise in and around the pump suction this means (that , $NPSHA < NPSHR$), A suction gage or manometer in the pump suction can be used to determine whether the NPSH available is equal to or greater than the NPSH required from the manufacturer's rating curve (NPSHR).
- Suction recirculation will produce loud crackling noise in and around the suction of the pump.

Fig.1.3.2. Suction recirculation

Fig.1.3.3. Examining the pressure side of the inlet vanes for suction recirculation damage

This is unlike cavitation damage from inadequate NPSH that occurs on the low pressure surface of the inlet vanes.

The onset of suction recirculation can be determined by an impact head tube (or pitot tube) installed at the impeller eye, with the tube directed into the eye, the reading in the normal pumping range is the suction head minus the velocity head at the eye. At the point of suction recirculation, however, the flow reversal from the eye impinges on the head tube with a rapid rise in the gage reading.

Fig.1.3.4. Installation of the impact head tube to detect suction recirculation during (a) normal flow and (b) recirculation flow

- Suction Strainer may have become blocked also check the foot valve of a pump suction pipe if it is clogged, as if the suction valve is closed. The water does not reach the pump and no flow or pressure is developed. .
- Sun some time warms suction line producing vapor .
- Source level may be below suction pipe entry. Just because the suction pipe can be seen entering a vessel, does not mean that the vessel is full, or full enough to permit pumping. Also if the suction pipe is insufficiently submerged, it may suck in air at certain times. Once air gets into the system, the pump does not function properly and it loses its pressure and flow.
- Choose the correct packing to use .

1.3.2 Pump unit :

- Suction pipe should be completely filled with liquid (primed).Energy in the form of velocities is imparted to the water by the rapid impeller rotation. The energy of the water at high velocities is gradually converted to a lower velocity with an increase in pressure energy by means of a gradually increased volume of the casing. This conversion of velocity into pressure effect will only work if the whole casing is full of water, so it is necessary for the pump casing to be full of water and fully primed.
- If there is a leak in the flange joint or threaded joints or any leakages in the suction pipe joints , you can observe it by performing a hydrostatic pressure test on the joints. This method may also detect weaknesses in the piping.
- Bents in the piping traps air pockets causing water hammering .

1.3.3 Delivery Pipe:

- Discharge recirculation will produce loud crackling noise with highest intensity is in the discharge volute or diffuser. To can reduce the effect of discharge recirculation by : (increasing the output capacity , install bypass between the discharge and the suction of the pump ,or modify the impeller design) .

Fig.1.3.5. Discharge recirculation

Fig.1.3.6. Damage to the pressure side of the vane from discharge recirculation

1.4. Mechanical Related Problems

There are many problems caused by the mechanical parts of the system (pumping unit and its component) and the major effect of any problem will damage this mechanical parts of the system.

We will discuss these problems which caused in the pump unit and the pipelines related to the mechanical problems .

1.4.1 Pump unit :

- Make sure that the motor or the prime mover is actually turning. Sometimes the prime mover may be turning, but the pump shaft is stationary. If the coupling bolts between the pump and the motor has been sheared off it may cause you to think that the pump is moving while actually only the motor is moving.
- Cavitation damage is the loss of material produced by the collapse of the vapor bubbles against the surfaces of the impeller or casing. Formation of these bubbles cannot occur if the net positive suction head available (supplied), or NPSHA, exceeds the NPSHR required .
- High thrust bearing temperatures and short thrust bearing life ,this is because of the axial thrust imposed in the direction of the shaft . Static thrust in excess of the bearing rating will cause cracking of the balls or rollers and of the race in rolling element bearings and metal scorings of the shoes in tilting-pad bearings. Bearing failure from dynamic loading in excess of the bearing rating will cause fatigue failures of the balls or rollers and race in rolling element bearings. It is important to differentiate clearly between static load failure and fatigue failure. This can be done by examination of a cross section of the failure zone under the microscope. Fatigue failure from dynamic loading will show a hammering effect caused by points of impact. Fatigue failure from excessive static loading will show metal fatigue without the hammering effect of impact loading.

Fig.1.4.1. Axial thrust

Shaft failure at the outboard, or unloaded, end of the shaft in multistage or double-suction pumps may be a fatigue failure in tension resulting from the high cyclic stresses induced in the shaft when the pump is operated in the discharge recirculation zone. Axial cyclic stresses can be reduced by increasing the pump output or, if this is not possible, by installing a

recirculation line to bypass sufficient flow to move the pump total flow rate beyond the point where damaging discharge recirculation occurs. The pump manufacturer can advise the recommended minimum continuous flow for a specific pump design.

If it is a static failure, the thrust can usually be reduced by restoration of the internal clearances. Most shaft and bearing failures from axial thrust, however, are fatigue failures. If the failure is a fatigue failure, the loading can usually be decreased by increasing the capacity of the pump. If this is not possible, shaft failures can be reduced by substituting a shaft material of higher endurance limit.

- High bearing temperatures with reduced life may be caused by the radial thrust .

Fig.1.4.2. Radial thrust

Static radial loads in excess of the bearing rating will cause cracking of the balls or rollers and the races in rolling element bearings. In the case of sleeve bearings, the bearing metal will be worn in one direction only and the journal will be worn uniformly. If the opposite is true (that is, the bearing is worn uniformly and the journal excessively in one direction), the cause of the failure is most likely unbalance or a bent shaft and not excessive bearing loads.

Also shaft failures from excessive radial loads usually occur at the midpoint of the shaft span in double-suction or multistage pumps.

Most bearing and shaft failures caused by excessive radial loads occur when the pump operates at low flow rates. Radial loads can be reduced by operating the pump at higher capacities or by installing a bypass from the pump discharge back to the pump suction or suction source .

- Instability of pump controls, vibration of suction and discharge piping, and high levels of pump noise are the effects of the *pressure pulsations* which occurs because the velocity distribution at the exit of the pump impeller is not uniform. As this non uniform flow passes the tongue of the pump casing, an abrupt change in the direction of the impeller exit velocity vector occurs at the proximity of the tongue. This produces a positive pressure wave at the pressure face and a negative pressure wave at the back face of the tongue. From this location, the positive pressure wave travels directly up the discharge line and the negative pressure wave travels completely around the pump casing and is attenuated before reaching the

discharge line. These positive pressure pulsations have a frequency equal to the product of the pump speed and the number of impeller vanes.

Pressure pulsations are usually measured with piezoelectric pressure transducers and recorded as peak-to-peak pressure pulsations over a broad frequency band. Recorded on tape or strip charts, a spectral analysis may be performed for any operating condition.

Fig.1.4.3. Piezoelectric pressure transducers amounted on the pump

Any welding at the top surface or metal removal at the outer periphery of the impeller should be done in such a manner that these surfaces remain smooth and concentric with the axis of rotation. Balance weights on surfaces normal to the axis of rotation should be applied or covered in such a manner that the surface remains flat, smooth, and normal to the axis of rotation.

- In some cases the driver may be damaged by overload when the error of reversed impeller might go undetected .
- No liquid delivered by pump because of lacking of prime (packing loose or defective, to allowing air leak into suction).
- No enough liquid delivered by pump , that is because of air leaking into stuffing box or defective packing . If no leakage occurs after reasonable gland , adjustment new packing may be needed or may be shaft or shaft sleeve beneath packing badly scored allowing air to be sucked into pump . Also check the smoothness of the shaft and shaft sleeve.
- Not enough pump pressure because of the defective packing .
- Pump works for a while and then quits because of air leaks into stuffing box .
- Pump takes too much power when the packing is too tight .
- Sometimes pump leaks excessively at stuffing and that is may occurs when the packing is defected or when we are using wrong type of packing also when the shaft or shaft sleeve scored.
- When stuffing box overheats , you check the packing if it is too tight or may be not lubricated or wrong type of packing or insufficient cooling water to jacket or the stuffing box may improperly packed .
- When the packing wears too fast we have to check the shaft or shaft sleeve if they worn or may be insufficient or no lubrication , also when the packing packed improperly or wrong grade of packing and some time the pulsating pressure on external seal liquid line may wears the packing .

- Seal spits and sputters (“face popping”) in operation , because the seal fluid vaporizing at seal interfaces .
- Seal drips steadily because the faces not flat or seal faces thermally distorted or Secondary seals nicked or scratched during installation or O-rings overaged or the secondary seals hard and brittle from compression set or the secondary seals soft and sticky from chemical attack or Spring failure or hardware damaged by erosion or may be the drive mechanisms corroded .
- Seal squeals during operation because of Amount of liquid inadequate to lubricate seal faces .
- Carbon dust accumulates on outside of gland ring because amount of liquid inadequate to lubricate seal faces or liquid film evaporating between seal faces .
- seal life is short when the fluid is abrasive or when the seal running too hot or if the equipment mechanically out of line .
- bearing failure can be diagnosis by the visual inspection , and it is caused by the contamination of the bearing oil by water or another liquid or by solid particles or because of high heat which is often caused by an overload on the bearing or by excessive lubrication or due to poor installation skills or care , the failure modes commonly found are :

1. Fatigue : which occurs because of cyclic loads normal to the bearing.

Fig.1.4.4. Babbitt fatigue

2. Wiping : results from surface – to – surface contact and smears the babbitt . The usual causes of wiping are a bearing overload , insufficient rotational speed to form a film and loss of lubricant .

Fig.1.4.5. Bearing wipe on a bearing due to temporary loss of lubricant

3. Overheating : is manifest by discoloration of the surface and cracking of the babbitt material . Overheating may be due to a lubrication problem in the bearing. Or may be due to having: the oil level too low or too high; the wrong grade of oil; moisture in the oil; too much grease inside the bearing; lack of lubrication, or foreign matter inside the lubricant, often due to shaft seal leakage.
4. Corrosion : is failure by chemical action .

Fig.1.4.6. Corrosion on lead-based babbitt bearing

5. Wear : results from contaminants in the film and is evidenced by scoring marks that may be localized or persist around a large circumferential region of the bearing .

In general Overloading of bearings can be a result of many different conditions: an unbalanced rotating element; a bent rotating shaft ; blocked impeller balance holes; cavitation; excessive axial thrust; excessive radial load caused by low flow operation or some mechanical failure inside the pump; excessive heating of bearings due to improper dissipation of heat; improper cooling of the bearings such as cooling the bearing housing with a water hose or some other similar system; increased pump internal running clearances around the wear rings; increasing the speed of the bearing; misalignment between the pump and its driver; operating the pump away from its best efficiency point (BEP) .

- Gland packing that are tightened too much will grip the shaft. When the shaft is rotated by the motor, the packing, made of hemp or cotton material will burn. This forms a layer of hard carbon on the surface of the packing. The layer of hard carbon is not flexible enough to seal the leak from the shaft and this give rise to bad leaks from the packing gland.

Fig.1.4.7. Components of sealing and packing

- Water seal pipe plugged causing overheating and leakage .
- Cyclic loading which effect the bearing is caused by the misalignment of the coupling .

Fig.1.4.8. Types of misalignment

- Check if the foundation not rigid enough because of cracked welds, or not tighten foundation bolts, or worn chocks .

1.4.2. Pipelines :

- may collapse because of a sudden power failure that leaves a pump and driver running free (Except for rare cases where a flywheel is provided) . The pressure in the discharge line falls rapidly and, under some circumstances may go below atmospheric pressure, both at the pump discharge and at any points of high elevation along the pipeline. The minimum pressure head may be low enough to cause vaporization followed by complete separation of the liquid column. When the liquid columns rejoin following separation, the shock pressures may be sufficient to rupture the pipe or the pump casing .

CONCLUSION

An engineer could use in order to diagnose the problem, the visual inspection, audio inspection, or vibration. In this seminar we try to mention the different problems of the centrifugal pumps and how to diagnose these problems in an expeditious way according to these methods .

REFERENCES

Books:

- 1- Igor J. Karassik , *Pump handbook* , third edition , printed by ASK Innotec, Arya Sepehr Kayhan , 2011.
- 2- Ron Palgrave , *Troubleshooting Centrifugal Pumps and Their Systems*, by Elsevier Science & Technology Books , January 2003.
- 3- *The Centrifugal Pump* , by Grundfos Research And Technology .
- 4- Kristoffer K. McKee, Gareth Forbes, Ilyas Mazhar, Rodney Entwistle and Ian Howard , " *A review of major centrifugal pump failure modes with application to the water supply and sewerage industries* " , Curtin University, Western Australia .

Web sites:

- 1- http://www.pumpingmachinery.com/pump_magazine/pump_articles/article_15/article_15.htm
- 2- <http://www.pumpfundamentals.com/tutorial1.htm>
- 3- <http://www.free-marine.com/index.html>
- 4- <http://mechanical-engineering.in/forum/topic/1060-pumps-used-in-cross-country-petroleum-pipelines/>
- 5- <http://www.hawsepipe.net/chiefhelppumps/centrifugal.htm>

Others:

- 1- *DiagnoPump Troubleshooting Software* , 2004 Yoon Chee Tuck, www.free-marine.com .